

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15878744

Appraisal of Firm Attributes on Share Price of Quoted Consumer Goods Firms in Nigeria (2014 to 2023)

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the value relevance of selected firm attributes on share price of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the study evaluated the effect of Earnings per Share (EPS), Book Value per Share (BVPS), and Return on Equity (ROE) on the share prices (SHP). The study adopted a robust regression dataset of 150 firm-year observations from the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). Descriptive statistics revealed notable dispersion across the variables, particularly in ROE and share price, suggesting that financial volatility across the sampled firms. The regression results show that ROE has a statistically significant and positive effect on share price, confirming that profitability measured through equity utilization is a key driver of market value. Contrarily, BVPS has a negative significant effect on share price, suggesting that firms with higher net asset values may not necessarily command higher market valuations, possibly due to concerns about inefficient asset utilization. EPS was found to be statistically insignificant in predicting share price within the sampled periods. These findings imply that investors place more emphasis on profitability efficiency than on absolute earnings or book value figures. Hence, the study submits that managers of the sampled consumer goods firms should focus on improving ROE and operational performance, while regulators strengthen financial disclosure standards to improve investor confidence in financial statements. Further research is encouraged to examine the role of non-financial indicators in explaining share price movements in emerging markets.

Keywords: Share Price, Earnings per Share, Book Value, Return on Equity, Value Relevance

1. INTRODUCTION

In the absence of adequate financial information, investors would not be in a position to make wise decisions, because it will be difficult to distinguish between potentially successful businesses (Ndubuisi et al., 2025). Existing and potential equity share investors often use financial information to make investment decision: they often use corporate financial information to review its financial health and operational profitability. This provides information about whether or not investing in the equity share of the company is a wise investment decision. The investors' decisions to buy or not to take stock depend upon financial information and the more investors use financial information, it is expected that rational decisions are made (Ayuba et al., 2018).

Generally, investors use financial statement information for investment decisions; government agencies need it particularly for tax purpose; while regulatory agencies use it to determine whether existing statutory pronouncements are complied with, among others. Financial statements still remain the most

important source of externally feasible information on companies. Value relevance of financial reporting is defined as the ability of financial numbers, contained in the financial statements, to explain the stock market measures. Financial data such as earnings per share are termed value relevant if they are significantly related to the dependent variable, which may be expressed by price return or abnormal return (Jeroh, 2020).

The identified problem stems from the fact that, investors often times are not well informed and as such depend on the information from speculators or other co-investors who have similar interest on the identical phenomenon. The study would portray to investors on how to make optimal use of audited financial statement which provides the mirror of the company's financial performance, financial position and changes in control of the owners and it would also serve as a reference source for future researchers. In light of this, this study seeks to evaluate the effect of financial attributes on share price of consumer goods in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual Review

A financial statement is a formal record of the financial activities and position of a business, person, or other entity. Relevant financial information is presented in an organized manner and a form easy to comprehend (Dave, 2018). Financial statements have the ability to perform a number of functions. They basically provide financial aid to managers in decision making, measurement or evaluation of a firm's performance, and also portray a firm's value. For disclosed financial information to be useful, it must be relevant and faithfully represent what it purports to represent. The usefulness of financial information is enhanced if it is comparable, verifiable, timely and understandable (Vishnani, Singh & Srivastava, 2024). Common firm attribute proxies are Earnings per Share (EPS), Book Value per Share, and Return on Equity. Specifically, EPS are considered the most frequently used financial information in value relevance studies used to examine its significant relationship with share price. Most studies on value relevance of earnings per share and share price results reported to be significant and positive related with share price (Shuaibu et al., 2019). Earnings per share is presented and published in the income statement of a company, it measures the profit allocated to each share. Profitability ratios are most popular and frequently used financial information variable. Meanwhile, book value per share (BPS) is used in measuring amount of assets a company has on behalf of each share. The company can have good record of past performance if the value of its book value is very high. Lastly, return on equity (ROE) is used in measuring amount of profit generated by company from the amount of money invested in the company by shareholders

2.3. Theoretical Review

The theoretical approach to the relationship between financial information and equity share investment can be discussed in terms of financial accounting theories and theory of equity share investment. Theories and theory of equity share investment. Theories of financial accounting consider such things as people's behaviour or people's needs as regards financial accounting information, or the reasons why people within organizations might elect to supply particular information to particular stakeholder groups (Deegan, 2019). This study look at Efficient-market hypothesis (EMH), information perspective theory, accounting theory, decision usefulness theory of financial information and signaling theory of financial information among other theories.

2.3.1. Efficient Market Hypothesis

Efficient market hypothesis (EMH) asserts that financial market is informational efficient. There are three major forms of hypothesis: "weak", "semi-strong", and "strong". Weak EMH claims that prices on traded assets. Semi-strong EMH states that prices reflect all past publicly available information and that price instantly change to reflect new public information. Strong EMH additionally claims that prices instantly

reflect even hidden or "insider" information. Efficient market theory implies that market will react quickly to new information (Deegan, 2019). Thus, it is important to know when the accounting report first became publicly known. The financial report is informative only if it provides data not previously known by the market.

Empirical Review

Sulistiawan and Rudiawarni (2025) evaluated the informativeness of accruals on stock prices of listed tech firms in Shanghai Stock Exchange. The authors confirmed that Research and Development (R & D) expenditures improve the relevancy of accruals of the sampled tech firms.

Ndubuisi, Henry and Horsfall (2025) evaluated the effect of firm attributes (EPS and firm size) on share price of 1,800 firm-year observations (2006-2023). The Fixed Effects Model (FEM) was adopted. The study confirmed that EPS and firm size significantly and positively influence share price, indicating investor preference for profitability and company scale. In contrast, audit firm size, firm age, leverage, and industry type show no significant effect, suggesting they are not primary drivers of stock performance. However, the interaction between firm size and industry type negatively affects share price, highlighting sectoral differences.

Olowe and Shehu (2021) investigated the IFRS adoption on value relevance of financial information of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study covered a period of eight years spanning 2008-2015. The dependent variable proxies share price while independent variables are earnings per share, change in earnings per share and book value per share. General least square is used for data analysis which findings revealed that both pre and post compulsory adoption of IFRS period financial information are value relevance over pre IFRS financial information.

Roca (2021) examined the influence of mandatory adoption of IFRS in Argentina on value relevance of accounting information. The study covered a period of twenty three years spanning 1997- 2019 panel data regression was used for analysis. The dependent variable proxies market value of equity while the independent variables are net earnings, book value of equity and sales growth rate. The regression analysis revealed that mandatory adoption of IFRS in Argentina does not improve the value relevance of any of the tested variables.

Lawal et al. (2020) investigated the impact of accounting numbers on stock prices in the Nigerian stock market. Ohlson 1995 model was used for data analysis. The dependent variable proxies last day share price while the independent variables are dividend per share and net book value. The findings show that there is a significant relationship between accounting information and share prices of companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange.

Ogbodo and Osisioma (2020) investigated the effect of value relevance of accounting information and share price: An empirical study on manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study covered a period of ten years spanning (2010- 2019), using Ordinary Least Square Regression (OLS) with the aid of E-view 9.0. The dependent variable is share price of the manufacturing Firms measured with the share price. While the independent variable, accounting information is measured with dividend per share. The findings revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between dividend per share The findings revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between dividend per share and the share price.

Etale, and Ombu (2019) carried out a study on the effect of financial accounting information relevance on share price of Unilever Nigeria PLC. The study covered a period of ten years spanning 2009- 2018 using linear regression. The proxies used were market price per share as dependent variable while earnings per share and dividend per share as the independent variables. The study revealed that earnings per share and dividend per share are not significantly related to market price per share.

Oroud, Islam, Salha, Ahmad and Ghazalat (2019) examined how audit quality moderate the relationship between accounting information on the share price in Jordan. The study covered a period of thirteen years spanning 2002-2014 using multivariable regression. The dependent variable is share price while

independent variables are current accruals, aggregate accruals and dividend yield. The findings revealed significant effects on the share price of the Jordanian companies listed on ASE.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted *expost facto* research since the variables under review are secondary data. The study population is twenty one (21) industrial goods firms covering the period of ten (10) years spanning from 2014 to 2023. However, fifteen (15) of the industrial goods firms were sampled. The study employed the robust regression approach. To ensure the model is robust and valid, the robust regression analysis was conducted. Data analysis is performed using Econometric Views (E-Views) 9.0. Various preliminary analysis conducted include descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, Multicollinearity test and Heteroskedascity test. The mathematical form of the model is presented in Equation 1:

$$SHP=f(EPS, BVPS,ROE).....3.1$$

Equation 1 is restated to capture error term as:

$$SHP=\beta_0+ \beta_1EPS+ \beta_2BVPS+ \beta_3ROE+Ut.....3.2$$

To address potential issues of Heteroskedasticity, Equation 2 is restated as:

$$= \beta_0+ \beta_1EPS+ \beta_2BVPS+ \beta_3ROE+Ut.....3.3$$

Where:

$$\widehat{SHP} = \text{fitted regression form}$$

Table 1: Operationalization of Variable

Variable	Description	Measurement/Unit	Type
Earnings per Share (EPS)	Profit allocated to each ordinary share	Naira per share	Continuous
Book Value per Share (BVPS)	Net asset value of a firm divided by total shares outstanding	Naira per share	Continuous
Return on Equity (ROE)	Profitability relative to shareholder equity	Ratio (%)	Continuous
Share Price (SHP)	Market price of a share at year-end	Naira	Continuous

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2025)

4. RESULTS

4.1 Preliminary Tests

The following preliminary tests were considered before the main regression was presented:

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Parameter	Mean	Maximum	Minimum
SHP	3.3059	61.32000	-70.87
BVPS	2.1603	11.4090	-6.6163
ROE	0.0793	0.5396	-0.5075
EPS	2.4162	36.4106	0.0858

Source: Authors’ Collation, 2025

From Table 2, the sampled firms reported an average value of ₦3.31 suggests that most of the sampled firms are relatively low-priced. However, the wide range between the maximum value of ₦61.32 and the unusually negative minimum (-₦70.87). Similarly, the mean BVPS value is ₦2.16, with a minimum of -₦6.62. The average ROE is 7.93%, reflecting moderate profitability across firms, though the large spread—from a maximum of 53.96% to a minimum of -50.75. EPS averaged ₦2.42, indicating moderate firm-level profitability, while the absence of negative EPS values suggests that firms with severe losses may have been excluded or reported near-zero earnings. Overall, the data shows substantial variability

across firms, justifying the use of robust regression techniques to mitigate the influence of outliers and ensure credible analysis of the value relevance of accounting information.

Table 3: Normality Test

Parameter	Jarque-Bera	Probability	Decision
SHP	1113.71	0.0000	Reject normality
BVPS	772.00	0.0000	Reject normality
ROE	101.23	0.0000	Reject normality
EPS	6200.52	0.0000	Reject normality

Source: Authors' Collation, 2025

From Table 3, SHP, BVPS, ROE, and EPS reported Jarque-Bera values of 1113.71, 772.00, 101.23, and 6200.52 alongside associated p-values significant at 1%. This suggests that the variables deviated sharply from normality assumption. This suggests that the RLS is the most appropriate estimation technique.

Table 4: Spearman rank-order Correlation Analysis

Correlation Cases	SHP	BVPS	ROE	EPS
SHP	1.0000			
BVPS	-0.1832	1.0000		
ROE	0.6895	0.0178	1.0000	
EPS	0.0870	-0.5302	0.1703	1.0000

The analysis reveals that SHP is positively and strongly correlated with SHP but ROE reported a positive weak correlation with SHP. However, BVPS has an inverse correlation with SHP. In terms of correlation among the independent variables, none of them reported possibility of high correlation. The multicollinearity test is presented in Table 5:

Table 5: Multicollinearity Tests

Variables	BVPS	ROE	EPS
VIF	1.0465	1.0716	1.0397
1/VIF	0.9556	0.9332	0.9618

Source: Authors' Collation, 2025

Table 5 reveals that the VIF values range between 1.0397 and 1.0716. This is below the benchmark value of 10. Also, the tolerance value (1/VIF) is above 0.10 suggesting that, the model is free from multicollinearity problems.

4.2. Regression Estimate and Discussion

Table 6: Robust Regression

Variable	Dependent Variable: SHP			Observations: 150	
	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.	
C	1.031202	0.108444	9.509063	0.0000	
BVPS	-1.269134	0.410848	-3.089058	0.0026	
ROE	32.12366	8.937389	3.594300	0.0005	
EPS	0.057764	0.221720	0.260525	0.7950	
Mean dependent var	3.305909	S.D. dependent var			12.82805

The regression analysis provides valuable insights into the extent to which key financial indicators: EPS, BVPS, and ROE influence the share prices of listed firms in Nigeria. Among the variables examined, ROE exhibits a strong and statistically significant positive relationship with share price, indicating that firms with higher profitability relative to shareholder equity are more likely to experience favorable investor valuation. This suggests that the market rewards firms that effectively utilize shareholders' funds to generate returns. On the other hand, BVPS demonstrates a statistically significant but negative

relationship with share price. This inverse association may reflect investor skepticism toward firms with high book values, possibly due to concerns about asset quality, inefficient resource utilization, or depressed market sentiment. EPS, a traditionally vital indicator of market value, was found to be statistically insignificant, implying that investors may not view reported earnings as a reliable driver of share price in the Nigerian context. This result may be attributed to potential earnings manipulation or the lack of earnings sustainability.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings underscore the importance of ROE as the most value-relevant financial metric influencing share prices in the Nigerian capital market. The unexpected negative impact of BVPS and the non-significance of EPS raise questions about the interpretability and reliability of certain accounting figures for investors. Therefore, stakeholders should exercise caution in relying solely on EPS or BVPS when making investment decisions. Based on these findings, it is recommended that corporate managers focus more on improving operational efficiency and enhancing profitability to increase ROE, thereby attracting investor interest. Investors, in turn, should prioritize firms with consistently strong ROE as a key indicator of financial performance. Regulatory authorities such as the SEC and NSE should also enhance financial reporting standards to strengthen the credibility of earnings disclosures and improve the overall transparency of financial statements. Future studies should consider incorporating qualitative factors such as governance quality, industry effects, and macroeconomic variables to deepen understanding of the determinants of share price in emerging markets like Nigeria.

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